

Synthesis and Structural Studies of the Complexes of $M(NCS)_2(NCSAg)_2$ [$M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ or Cu^{II}] with Ureas, Amides and Acetanilides

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A new series of bimetallic tetrathiocyanate complexes, $L_2M(NCS)_2(NCSAg)_2$; where $M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and $L=$ urea (u), thiourea (tu), ethylenethiourea (etu), *N*-allylurea (Nau), acetamide (actm), benzamide (bnzm), acetanilide (actn), bromoacetanilide (Br-actn) and acetylacetanilide (ac-actn) have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral studies. These studies indicate monomeric bridged structure for all complexes supported by softness calculations. Stability constants of the complexes are calculated from carbonyl stretching frequency of amide in the complexes. TGA shows earlier decomposition of ligand compared to thiocyanate.

SEVERAL studies have been made on the coordination behaviour of mixed metal tetrathiocyanates, $MM'(NCS)_4$ ($M=Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn$; $M'=Zn, Cd, Hg$) and their complexes¹⁻³. The reported⁴ polymeric thiocyanate bridged complexes, $Co(NCS)_2(NCSAg)_2$ and $Cu(NCS)_2(NCSAg)_2$ have recently been used as Lewis bases along with their Ni^{II} analogues⁵. In this communication, we present the study of coordination behaviour of these complexes towards ureas, thioureas and amide derivatives *i.e.*, oxygen and sulphur donors.

Experimental

Reagent grade hydrated metal nitrates and AnalaR potassium thiocyanate (BDH) were used. Ligands and solvents were used after purification by known methods. $M(NCS)_2(NCSAg)_2$ were prepared as described earlier⁵. $Co(NCS)_2(NCSAg)_2 \cdot 2L$ ($L=tu, etu, u, Nau, actm, bnzm, actn, Br-actn$ and $ac-actn$) complexes were prepared by stirring 5 mmol $Co(NCS)_2(NCSAg)_2$ with 20 mmol solution of each ligand in 50 ml ethanol for 6-8 h. Blue or green complexes precipitated were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by acetone and dried in vacuum. Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} analogues were similarly prepared.

Analysis of the complexes and physical measurements were made as described earlier^{5,10,11}. Thermogravimetric analysis of the complexes were made on a TGA analyser model TGA-FCI-P & D, Sindri, India.

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra: All complexes show (Table 2) the presence of one sharp and a shoulder band of

ν_{CN} , ν_{CS} and δ_{NCS} at 2120-2140, 735-755 and 440-455 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicating the presence of bridged thiocyanates^{1,19-14}. Shoulder band is observed due to splitting of this degenerate band on account of bent $M-NCS-Ag$ bond. A second sharp and intense band is observed in these regions at $\sim 2105, 710$ and $415 cm^{-1}$, respectively, showing the presence of S-bonded terminal thiocyanates^{12-14,17}. However, for thiourea complexes these bands are observed at $\sim 2070, 825$ and $475 cm^{-1}$, respectively, showing the presence of N-bonded terminal thiocyanates^{12-14,17}.

In ν_{M-NCS} region, three bands are observed at 250-315 cm^{-1} due to splitting of the $M-NCS$ degenerate bands^{15,16,28}. In ν_{M-O} and $\nu_{M-S(L)}$ regions, two to three bands are observed at 350-400 cm^{-1} which are in the range of $M-L$ stretching frequency of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} complexes^{1,8-19}. These bands are absent in the case of thiourea which shows coordination to Ag^I . In ν_{Ag-S} region one or two bands are observed at 205-240 cm^{-1} . All ligands show features of coordination through amide oxygen or thioamide sulphur.

Molar conductance, magnetic moment and electronic spectra:

Co^{II} complexes: All are coloured blue or green except urea complex which is pink. They are insoluble in common organic solvents except dimethylsulfoxide in which they dissolve giving pink solutions. Conductance values in dmsO (Table 1) indicate that all the complexes are non-conducting. Molecular weight could not be determined due to lack of sufficient solubility in the solvent.

Pink coloured complex having B.M. value 4.95 and the position of bands in electronic spectra¹⁸ shown in Table 3 indicate that Co^{II} is octahedral in

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL RESULTS AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA

Sl. No.	Complexes	m.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.)				Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
			Co, Ni or Cu	Ag	N	S	
1.	Co(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 4u	185*	8.0 (7.87)	26.9 (27.57)	22.7 (22.50)	17.0 (17.13)	37.4
2.	Co(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2tu	170	8.7 (8.95)	33.2 (32.78)	16.9 (17.04)	29.3 (29.13)	28.5
3.	Co(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2etu	160	8.2 (8.30)	31.1 (30.38)	16.0 (15.75)	27.3 (27.00)	35.6
4.	Co(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2Nau	230*	8.4 (8.35)	31.2 (30.55)	15.7 (15.84)	17.9 (18.10)	43.5
5.	Co(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2aotm	245*	9.0 (9.44)	35.1 (34.56)	13.1 (13.44)	20.7 (20.48)	32.7
6.	Co(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2bnzm	210*	7.7 (7.88)	29.1 (28.84)	11.3 (11.21)	16.9 (17.09)	42.7
7.	Co(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2actn	245*	7.7 (7.59)	28.2 (27.80)	11.0 (10.81)	16.7 (16.47)	27.8
8.	Co(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2Br-actn	220*	6.4 (6.31)	22.8 (23.10)	9.1 (8.98)	14.0 (13.69)	24.5
9.	Co(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2ac-actn	230*	6.7 (6.61)	24.5 (24.19)	9.8 (9.40)	13.9 (14.33)	31.3
10.	Ni(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2u	210*	9.5 (9.41)	35.1 (34.45)	18.6 (17.86)	20.3 (20.41)	43.7
11.	Ni(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2tu	200*	9.1 (8.95)	33.0 (32.78)	17.2 (17.04)	28.8 (29.13)	38.8
12.	Ni(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2etu	150	8.4 (8.30)	31.1 (30.38)	16.0 (15.75)	26.9 (27.00)	40.3
13.	Ni(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2Nau	205*	8.3 (8.35)	29.8 (30.55)	16.1 (15.84)	17.8 (18.10)	49.2
14.	Ni(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2actm	280*	9.4 (9.44)	35.3 (34.56)	13.5 (13.44)	20.7 (20.48)	41.8
15.	Ni(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2bnzm	220*	8.0 (7.88)	29.2 (28.84)	12.8 (11.21)	16.8 (17.09)	34.4
16.	Ni(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2actn	200*	7.7 (7.59)	28.1 (27.80)	9.2 (10.80)	16.5 (16.47)	49.9
17.	Ni(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2Br-actn	225*	6.4 (6.31)	22.8 (23.10)	9.0 (8.89)	14.0 (13.69)	25.1
18.	Ni(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2ac-actn	220*	6.5 (6.61)	24.4 (24.19)	9.5 (9.40)	14.2 (14.33)	32.9
19.	Cu(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2u	230*	9.9 (9.98)	34.5 (34.23)	18.1 (17.75)	20.3 (20.38)	17.6
20.	Cu(NOS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂ 2tu	150	9.4 (9.50)	33.3 (32.58)	16.7 (16.89)	29.2 (28.96)	39.6

* Decomposed.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL BAND ASSIGNMENTS

Sl. No.**	ν_{CN}	ν_{CO}	ν_{CS}	δ_{NCS}	$\nu_{\text{M-O}} (\text{L})$	$\nu_{\text{M-NSC}}$	$\nu_{\text{Ag-SCN}}$
1.	2120s, 2108sh	1657s	745m, 730sh	455s, 445sh	390sh, 380m, 365w	300w, 275w, 250w	220m, 230w
2.	2130sh, 2120s, 2107sh	—	825w, 750m, 705w	475s, 455s, 445sh	—	300m, 285m, 260w	228m, 220w
3.	2130sh, 2120s, 2107sh	—	760m, 700sh, 710w	465s, 450sh, 410w	290w, 275w*	305w, 280w, 260w	232m, 210w
4.	2130s, 2120sh, 2105sh	1665m	750s, 740w	450s, 440sh, 410s	395w, 385w, 365w	305s, 280sh, 250m	225s, 210m
5.	2125s, 2108s	1660s	755s, 740w, 710w	455sh, 445w, 415m	400w, 375w, 350sh	307s, 290sh	225s, 215m
6.	2130s, 2110sh, 2100s	1640s	754m, 744m, 710m	450sh, 440s, 415m	398w, 377w, 350sh	300sh, 288s, 265m	230m, 210sh
7.	2120s, 2105sh	1650s	752s, 745s	442m, 435m	390w, 370w, 345sh	307s, 269sh	230w
8.	2130s, 2120sh	1652s	755sh, 745s, 710w	450sh, 440s, 415s	392s, 375m, 350w	308s, 255sh	225w
9.	2130s, 2110sh	1653s	750s, 730sh	455s, 435m	390w, 378w, 345w	295w, 275m	225s
10.	2120sb	1600s	752s, 705w	455w, 442w	385w, 372w, 355w	305w, 290w	230m, 215m
11.	2122s, 2070s	—	825m, 745m	480s, 450sh	—	310m, 285w	235m, 215w
12.	2132sh, 2118sh	—	750m, 745sh	455sh, 445s	285w, 255w*	280s, 250s	225m, 205sh
13.	2125s, 2110sh	1650s	752w, 704m	465m, 442w	390m, 380w, 370w	300w, 280s, 250s	225m, 205sh
14.	2140sh, 2133s	1645s	750w, 735w	465sh, 455s	400w, 380w, 360w	305w, 275w, 250s	230s
15.	2142sh, 2135s, 2100s	1640s	750m, 720w	445s, 455sh	390m, 380m, 365w	312m, 305w	222m, 210sh
16.	2138sh, 2125s	1652s	750s, 710w	440m, 430w	380w, 320w	305m, 250mb	230m
17.	2143s, 2112sh	1654s	745sh, 735s	453sh, 443s	328s	303w, 240m	226s
18.	2143sb	1660m	743s, 725sh	458s, 443sh	400w, 360w, 330w	295w, 282w	228s
19.	2138s, 2120sh	1665w	735s, 725sh	440s, 415s	395w, 370w, 355w	320w, 300w, 280w	240w, 220w
20.	2125s, 2070s	—	815m, 760m	475m, 456w, 443s	—	315w, 280w	230m, 220sh

* = $\nu_{\text{M-S}}(\text{L})$, ** Corresponding complexes in Table 1 : M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}.

s = sharp, m = medium, sh = shoulder, w = weak, b = broad.

TABLE 3—MAGNETIC MOMENT, ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BAND ASSIGNMENTS AND SPECTRAL PARAMETERS (cm⁻¹)

Complexes	ν_3	ν_2	ν_1	Dq	B'	β	μ_{eff} B.M.
(u) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	20280	18580	9800	987	848	0.87	4.95
(tu) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	16130	8390	—	492	646	0.67	4.40
(etu) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	16140	7270	—	422	716	0.74	4.35
(Nau) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	16200	8230	—	485	659	0.68	4.37
(actn) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	16250	8440	—	499	648	0.66	4.38
(ac-actn) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	16340	9950	—	587	836	0.80	3.00
(etu) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	15750	—	—	—	—	—	0.00
(u) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	27000	16000	9880	980	906	0.87	3.10
(tu) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	26650	15350	9150	910	980	0.94	3.05
(actm) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	26200	15750	9800	970	856	0.83	3.15

urea complex. Dq value (987 cm⁻¹), calculated by Tanabe and Sugano method²⁵ also support this view. B.M. values in the range 4.35-4.40 of all blue or green complexes and their electronic spectral bands shown in Table 3, indicate tetrahedral coordination of Co^{II}. Dq values (422-500 cm⁻¹) support this coordination¹⁹.

On the basis of the above results and ir spectra, following structures can be proposed for Co^{II} complexes.

Fig. 1a

Fig. 1b. L=etu, Nau, actm, bnzm, actn, ac-actn, Br-actn.

These structures are probable due to the following reasons :

(1) They show the presence of bridging thiocyanates, coordinated through nitrogen end to Co^{II} and through sulphur end to Ag^I according to HSAB principle²⁰.

(2) Thiourea being softer than -NCS (Table 4) prefers Ag^I, while other ligands being harder than -SCN prefer Co^{II} for coordination.

(3) A higher value of total softness difference, $\Delta TE_n^{\ddagger}(M-M')$ in a bimetallic bridged complex, indicates greater stability^{20-24,27}. Higher value of $\Delta TE_n^{\ddagger}(Co-Ag)$ is obtained on considering thiourea attached to Ag^I while for other complexes, higher values are obtained when ligands were attached to Co^{II} (Table 4).

TABLE 4—SOFTNESS VALUES OF LIGANDS AND THEIR MATCHING WITH M(II) AND AG(I) (M=Co, Ni, Cu)

E _m [‡] (Ligand)	$\Delta TE_n^{\ddagger}(M-Ag)^*$		
	(a)	(b)	
(u) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-10.41	24.92	16.90
(tu) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-7.63	19.36	19.67
(etu) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-13.32	30.74	13.98
(actm) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-10.57	25.24	16.73
(bnzm) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-10.57	25.24	16.73
(u) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-10.41	24.46	16.44
(tu) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-7.63	18.90	19.21
(etu) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-13.32	30.30	13.52
(actm) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-10.57	24.78	16.27
(bnzm) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-10.57	24.78	16.27
(u) ₂ Cu(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-10.41	24.62	15.60
(tu) ₂ Cu(NCS) ₂ (NCSAg) ₂	-7.63	18.06	18.37

*Obtained on considering ligand attached (a) to M(II) and

(b) to Ag^I.

E_n[‡] values for (Co) = -0.74, (Ag) = -2.98, (Ni) = -0.28,

(Cu) = -0.55 ;

E_m[‡] values for (-SCN⁻) = -5.62, (-NCS⁻) = -8.79.

Ni^{II} complexes : All complexes are nonconducting in dmsO, green in colour, paramagnetic with B.M. values in the range 3.00-3.15 and decomposed above 200°. However, etu complex is yellow, diamagnetic and melts at 150°. The presence of weak broad band at ~15750 cm⁻¹ in electronic spectra due to ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} transition^{10,19}, sharp melting point and diamagnetic nature of etu complex, suggest square planar geometry around Ni^{II}.

Urea, thiourea and acetamide complexes show the presence of two bands in electronic spectra at 26200-27000 and 15360-16000 cm⁻¹ due to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (P), ν_3 and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (F), ν_2 transitions, respectively, indicating octahedral Ni^{II} in these complexes^{19,25}. Octahedral coordination is achieved by axial coordination through terminal thiocyanate groups of the second molecule, in these complexes. Thiourea being softer than -NCS, is shown attached to Ag^I (Fig. 2a) while other ligands being harder than -SCN, are attached to Ni^{II} according to HSAB principle.

Electronic spectra of ac-actn complex shows two bands at ~16340 and 9950 cm⁻¹ due to ³T₁ → ³T₁ (P), ν_3 , and ³T₁ → ³A₂, ν_2 transitions, respectively,

indicating tetrahedral Ni^{II} . Cross linking is not achieved in this structure probably due to steric hindrance caused by large acetyl-acetanilide molecules.

On the basis of these results and ir discussion, we may propose the following structures to the octahedral Ni^{II} complexes

Fig. 2a L = u, actm

Fig. 2b

In Fig. 2b axial linkage is achieved by NH_2 groups of thioamide.

Cu^{II} complexes : Both the complexes are yellow in colour which turns brown on long exposure to light. They are nonconducting in dmsO and have B.M. values 1.77 and 1.80, respectively.

Electronic spectra shows the presence of two bands in the ranges 18500-19000 and 14200-15384 cm^{-1} which are consistent with tetragonal copper(II) complexes^{11,26}.

IR discussion and softness values (Table 4) indicate the attachment of urea to Cu^{II} and thiourea to Ag^{I} , supporting the structures given for Ni^{II} complexes (Fig. 2a, b).

Stability constants : The stability constants of the complexes where ligands coordinate through carbonyl oxygen, have been determined using the following equation⁶⁻⁸

$$\log K = 0.042 \nu_{\text{CO}} - 64.428$$

Using this equation we have calculated log K values from shifted carbonyl stretching frequencies of the complexes and presented in Table 5. These values are found in reciprocal relationship with the amount of shift, $\Delta \nu_{\text{CO}}$. The complexes are found in the following order of increasing stability

For a particular ligand, say urea, the stability increases from Co^{II} complexes to Cu^{II} complexes

Table 5 shows direct relationship of decomposition temperatures with stability constants of the complexes.

TABLE 5—DEPENDENCE OF log K VALUES ON DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURE AND $\Delta \nu_{\text{CO}}$

Complexes	Decomp. temp. °C	$\Delta \nu_{\text{CO}}$	log K
$(u)_2\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{NCSAg})_2$	180	69	3.528
$(u)_2\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{NCSAg})_2$	240	66	3.696
$(u)_2\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{NCSAg})_2$	280	62	3.720
$(\text{bnzm})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{NCSAg})_2$	200	48	4.200
$(\text{actm})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{NCSAg})_2$	210	37	4.788
$(\text{actn})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{NCSAg})_2$	240	25	4.872
$(\text{Br-actn})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{NCSAg})_2$	260	21	4.950
$(\text{ac-actn})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{NCSAg})_2$	280	23	5.040

Thermogravimetric analysis : The TGA curves of the complexes (Fig. 3 and 4) show three major inflections. First inflection lies in the temperature range 200-400°. The percent weight loss in this range is approximately equivalent to the ligand loss. The percent weight loss in the second inflection (500-700°) is found nearly equivalent to the decomposition of the complexes, $\text{M}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{NCSAg})_2$, to metal(II) cyanides and silver sulphide. The percent weight loss in the third inflection (900-1050°) is found nearly equivalent to the decomposition of metal cyanides and silver sulphide to metals. Above this temperature weight loss almost ceased.

In case of $\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{NCSAg})_2 2\text{tu}$, noticeable increase in weight is observed at 500-700° which may be due to oxidation of Co^{II} to Co^{III} by air. Co^{II} compounds are actually oxidised by air to Co^{III} compounds above 700° in certain cases. At this stage, we are unable to explain the minute increase in weight in this temperature range for Ni^{II} complex, $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{NCSAg})_2 2\text{u}$.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

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